

Supplemental materials

Figure S1

Supplementary Figure 1. Detection of phosphorylated myosin light chain 2 (pMLCII) in Y-27632-treated iPSC-RPE cells. (A) IHC for pMLCII (green) in human iPSC-RPE cells without or with 10 μM Y-27632 in time-course analysis (15 min, 30 min, 60 min, 3 h, 6 h, and 24 h). **(B)** IHC for pMLCII (green) and phalloidin (red) in human iPSC-RPE cells with 0, 0.1, 1, 10, and 100 μM Y-27632 in dosage analysis.

Figure S2

Supplementary Figure 2. Suppression of production of inflammatory cytokines/chemokines in Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells and capacity of Y-27632 to suppress the activation of lymphocytes *in vitro*. We examined *IL-6*, *TNF- α* , *CXCL11/I-TAC*, and *CCL2/MCP-1* in Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells by qRT-PCR and ELISA. **(A)** In qRT-PCR, Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells expressed less mRNA for *IL-6*, *CXCL11/I-TAC*, and *CCL2/MCP-1*, although the RPE cells did not express mRNA for *TNF- α* . ND, not detected. **(B)** In a dose-dependent assay with Y-27632 (1, 10, 50, and 100 μ M), Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells, especially 10, 50, and 100 μ M, produced less *CCL2/MCP-1* mRNA compared with non-treated RPE cells. **(C)** We obtained similar results with ELISA for CCL2/MCP-1: Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells poorly produced CCL2/MCP-1 protein. $**P < 0.005$, $*** P < 0.0005$ as compared to the control (non-treated RPE cells, open bar). **(D-F)** Capacity of Y-27632 to suppress activation of lymphocytes *in vitro*. We also examined whether Y-27632 directly suppressed the activation of lymphocytes. **(D)** Y-27632 directly suppressed cell proliferation of immune cells: CD4⁺/Ki-67⁺ (proliferative helper T cells), CD8⁺/Ki-67⁺ (proliferative cytotoxic T cells), and CD11b⁺/Ki-67⁺ (proliferative monocytes) when mixed lymphocyte reactions (MLR) were performed by FACS analysis. **(E)** In a dose-dependent assay with Y-27632 (1, 10, 50 μ M), Y-27632 greatly suppressed cell proliferation of these lymphocytes. **(F)** Y-27632 significantly suppressed the production of IFN- γ inflammatory cytokines in Y-27632 and PBMC cocultures. $*P < 0.05$, $** P < 0.005$ as compared to the control (PBMC mix without Y-27632, open bar).

Figure S3

Supplementary Figure 3. Toxicity of iPS-RPE cells by Y-27632 treatment. We examined the expression of RPE-specific markers such as VEGF-A, PEDF, RPE65, bestropin-1, Pax6, and tyrosinase in Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells. **(A)** In qRT-PCR, there were no statistical differences between Y-27632-treated and non-treated RPE cells. **(B)** In IHC, Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells and non-treated cells clearly expressed VEGF on their surfaces. Isotype = RPE staining with rabbit IgG. Scale bar in IHC = 50 μ m. **(C)** There were no significant differences between Y-27632-treated and non-treated RPE cells in the expression of VEGF. **(D)** However, there were significant differences between Y-27632-treated and non-treated cells in the expression of PEDF, indicating that Y-27632-treated iPS-RPE cells greatly produced PEDF growth factor, which is a RPE-specific marker, when compared with non-treated cells. Thus, RPE cells exposed to the ROCK inhibitor experienced no harm or toxicity. * $P < 0.05$ between two groups. n.s., not significant.

Figure S4

Supplementary Figure 4. *In vivo* retinal toxicity in a non-human primate by Y-27632 treatment. We administrated saline only as a control into the right eye (**A**) and Y-27632 in saline into the left eye (**B**) (20-40 μ L, respectively) in a normal adult cynomolgus monkey. We then measured focal ERG in the retina of Y-27632 in the left eye and control right eye. Compared with pre-operative data (Pre-OPE), ERG was temporary decreased in both retinas at 1 month after administration, and then the data recovered to baseline at 2-3 months. There were no significant differences between them after a six-month evaluation, indicating that Y-27632 administration in the eye did not change retinal sensitivity. (**C**) Similarly, there were no differences between Y-27632-injected and control retinas in color fundus; 6M, six months. (**D**) In IHC, neural retina & RPE clearly expressed RBP3/IRBP (a marker for neural retina and RPE cells), and the RPE cell layer clearly expressed collagen IV (a marker for basement membrane). These results indicated that there was no retina damage or toxicity after Y-27632 administration *in vivo*. Scale bar in IHC = 20 μ m.

Figure S5

Supplementary Figure 5. Transplantation of allogeneic iPS-RPE cells in an *in vivo* animal model (without Y-27632, control eye). Without Y-27632, we transplanted allogeneic iPS-RPE cells (46a line) by the same method. (A) In color fundus, we found pigmented graft cells, but they were not expanded (clump-like)

in the retina of the monkey right eye at 4 and 24 weeks, and there were no abnormal signs such as rejection at 24W FA (right panel). **(B)** We found graft RPE cells without any abnormal signs in the subretinal space at 24W in OCT evaluation. Compared with retinal sections in the right eye without Y-27632 **(C)**, the *in vivo* expanded graft RPE cells were seen throughout the retinal sections from the left eye **(D)**. Arrows show transplanted graft iPS-RPE cells. Scale bar in IHC = 20 μ m.